

NNLM Impact Quick Reference

What is IMPACT?

- Impact is the provable effects of our work in the real world; Impact is the measurable change which occurs because of our efforts – a term for the change not the process.
- It's important to focus on making impact meaningful to you, your partners and the community, and our work and mission.
- Good impact is achieved by mapping, connecting, and assessing the results of the path from our efforts to effect(s). Impact is not defined by how big it is, when it happens, or the route taken to get there. Impact can happen quickly, take a long time, and/or require a series of smaller sequenced changes. There is no 'one size fits all' approach.

mapping, connecting,
& assessing
resulting change

impact

What isn't IMPACT?

- Dissemination or engagement ("knowledge mobilization") – the act of communicating research – this is vital for making research visible, but it is not impact until it is used; the process by which our research is connected to the real world
- Citations – these indicators measure attention, rather than demonstrate or measure real-world change
- Other attention measures – social media followers and retweets show attention, but do not show change.

NNLM Resources

- [NNLM Impact Story Reporter](#) (REDCap)
- Best Practices for Good Data
- Email: NEC@northwestern.edu
- Online Request Form: [NEC Support Request Form](#)
- [NEC Zenodo Community](#) | [LinkedIn](#) | [X/Twitter](#) | [NEC on NNLM.gov](#)

References

- Bayley, J. (2023). Creating Meaningful Impact: The Essential Guide to Developing an Impact-Literate Mindset. Emerald Publishing Limited. <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/978-1-80455-189-920231016/full/html>
- Bayley, Julie, and David Phipps. "Impact literacy workbook." (2019). <https://www.emeraldgrouppublishing.com/sites/default/files/2020-06/Impact%20Literacy%20Workbook%20Final.pdf>
- Reed, M.S., Rudman, H. Re-thinking research impact: voice, context and power at the interface of science, policy and practice. Sustain Sci 18, 967–981 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01216-w>

Key Terms

- **Activity** Actions taken or work performed through which inputs, such as funds, technical assistance and other types of resources, are mobilized to produce specific outputs.
- **Inputs** The financial, human, material (in-kind), and institutional (including technological and information) resources used for the intervention. Note: It is important to include not only the resources of a funding or implementing organization but the totality of resources of all involved organizations, the community and the local environment used for the intervention.
- **Outputs** The products, capital goods and services that result from an intervention. Outputs may also include changes resulting from the intervention that contribute to the achievement of outcomes. Outputs include changes in knowledge, skills, or abilities produced by the activities. Note: Outputs are within the control of the implementing team and attributable to it.
- **Outcomes** The short-term and medium-term effects of an intervention's outputs. Note: Outcomes are often changes that occur between the completion of outputs and the achievement of impacts.
- **Impacts** The higher-level effects of an intervention's outcomes. The ultimate effects or longer-term changes resulting from the intervention. Such impacts can include intended and unintended, positive or negative higher-level effects. Note: Impacts is used here in the plural in reference to its meaning as a type or level of result, as distinct from the impact criterion.
- **Effects** Intended or unintended changes due directly or indirectly to an intervention.
- **Goal** The higher-order objective to which an intervention is intended to contribute.
- **Evaluation** The systematic and objective assessment of a planned, ongoing or completed intervention, its design, implementation and results. The aim is to determine relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact and sustainability. Evaluation also refers to the process of determining the worth or significance of an intervention. An evaluation should provide information that is credible and useful, enabling the incorporation of lessons learned into decision-making processes. Note: Evaluation in some instances involves the definition of appropriate standards and criteria, the examination of performance against those standards, an assessment of actual and expected results and the identification of relevant lessons and recommendations. Though evaluation deals with the assessment of relevance, coherence, effectiveness, efficiency, impact and sustainability, not all evaluations will cover all of these criteria to the same degree or at all.